

Personality Traits Influencing Style Adoption among Youth in Khairpur Mir's

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ABSTRACT

To investigate the degree to which various traits of personality influencing adoption style among youth of Khairpur Mir's. The study has utilized a questionnaire survey. Participants were 86 from Khairpur Mir's. A 54-item questionnaire survey was used that measured the personality traits influence on style adoption where as style adoption was dependent variable and personality traits were independent variables. Influence on style adoption was measured using seven independent variables namely: Knowledge, Attitude, Fashion consciousness, susceptibility to interpersonal influence, Need for uniqueness, Individualism/collectivism and Masculinity/ Femininity. To determine its reliability, data was entered in SPSS 16 for checking Cronbach's alpha than factors were explored by using data reduction technique and finally linear regression with stepwise method was applied to check the influence of personality traits influencing style adoption among youth of Khairpur Mir's. Among all variables the influence of Attitude, Susceptibility to interpersonal influence and Individualism/collectivism on style adoption is very much effective and shows strong and positive relation with style adoption. This study was conducted in Khairpur Mir's to know the level of style adoption among youth.

Keywords: Personality traits influencing Style adoption.

1. INTRODUCTION

Personality is the set of psychological traits and mechanisms within the individual that are organized and relatively enduring and that influence his or her interactions with, and adaptations to, the intra psychic, physical, and social environments. We can also say that personality is an individual's unique constellation of consistent behavioral traits. Here in this research paper we have used the research paper of Marike Venter as a base paper to investigate the personality traits influencing style adoption among the youth in Khairpur Mir's. To examine style adoption, to identify the personality traits that influence style adoption among youth, to compare post modern versus classic style adoption and to get a better understanding of the role of gender and style adoption among youth in Khairpur Mir's.

According to many researchers view about personality traits is that personality traits are naturally obtained from birth and are invariable but at the same time other researchers argue that personality traits are growing steadily and may even change although it may be a natural mood never changes. Individuals with different personality traits not only have different job performance but also evaluate the performance of a single person differently. Personality traits will provide a form of

personal readiness to respond in the certain way. In fact, personality traits due to the influence on the attitudinal variables, will affect indirectly human behavior. This is also reason that personality of consumer towards buying any product differ from person to person. One of the most important factors in the development of attitudes and behavior of person is personality. Usually people with special personality have special attitudes that are consistent with their personality pattern. Personality of anyone is the major dimension and psychological structure which helps in the formation of life style. There have been various theories from the past to the present about individual differences and personality.

If we look behind, many psychologists have quoted their own experience about the personality and its traits. Among those Aristotle is one and known as a great personality psychologist of his time. He has expressed his views in one of his book "The Nicomachean Ethics" that "Each person is, in certain respects, like all other persons, like some other persons, and like no other person". According to him personality is the set of different psychological traits mean that psychological traits are characteristics that describe ways in which people are different from each other. He argued that someone is shy is to mention one way in which he or she differs from others who are more outgoing. According to him, traits are basically those which define ways people

are similar. For example, people who are shy are similar to each other in that they are anxious in social situations, particularly situations in which there is an audience focusing attention on them.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The author of research paper gives the view about personality as the central emotional uniqueness that decides and imitates how an individual react to its surroundings. According to him, unique identity, formation to point out sentimental, and motivational processes towards getting entity and combined objectives, as conserving logic of individual characteristics is being absorbed by personality, which classify personality as reliable reaction to ecological stimuli. (Bandura, et al., 1997, 1996, 1995)

The research paper is about the international style adoption business that is swiftly rising, and describes the style actions held in several rising markets. Researcher gives the idea that personality theories are given to judge the personality of people as theories given by Freudian and Neo-Freudian regarding personality to know personal distinctiveness of people. Furthermore researcher in this paper has also discussed the trait theory of personality by concluding the idea as the amount of pre-determined features called traits in which people are different from each other. Researcher said trait as any unique, moderately continuing method in which one person vary from other by giving three of its features: It is very much frequent to people, it is unconditional to all people and traits is comparatively constant and exercised reasonably general result on behavior of person. It can be the best tool to measure the behavior of person. (Poley, et al., 1976 & 2001)

This research paper states the personality characteristics through its communication with style adoption among the individuals. Researcher believes that current example on fashion comprise of unique appearance through the connection with fashion, somewhat than by fashion for being happy or unhappy. Author also gives the idea about the impulsive options of fashion and change fashion character that is a basic idea of present fashion, which is the destruction of fashion signs that guide to fashion uniqueness. Researcher concludes that the new fashion adopted in ones personality is visible by unique character and its uniqueness. (Kjeldgaard, et al., 1999 & 2009)

This research paper speaks about the personality style of societal system users of individuals and its impact and use on the famous social network place facebook

resulting from social media. Researcher gives idea about the personality style and personality traits to judge the level of the persons using the social network. Furthermore the attitude and motivation level of persons is analyzed that how much time is given by individuals to this social site. The main purpose of this is to know the connection among the personality, personality traits, and personality type and facebook users. Researcher found the results that persons who are giving three hours daily to facebook are the real purpose users while others are only visitors. (Harbaugh, 2010)

Here in this research paper author has focused on the personality as a basic measure towards analyzing the actual behavior and response of the consumer. The paper is comprised of the deferent matters associated with personality and personlogy of consumers. However author has also focused on the personality traits for knowing the best connection among the personality, trait, consumer and consumer's response towards the products. Somewhat it's easy to know and some where it's hard to judge the personality of consumers. Researcher believes that person character are associated and connected with the personality of consumers and it direct impacts the behavior of the consumers. Furthermore he also concludes that psychological factors can affect the personality of consumers and their decisions. (Baumgartner, 2002)

This research paper states the idea about individual perceptions with respect to different psychological theories and its relation with the cost in shape of motivation of the individuals towards their personality. The result have lead to the concept that human capability is direct related with human decision and needs and gives the idea that human preferences are unlimited. The more the people, more will be desires with respect to their personal characters and capability of fulfilling their choices. Furthermore, member really gave the description better than succeeding approval with their assortment. (Iyengar, et al., 2000)

This research study argues that personality beliefs are directly connected with the feelings of personality and adaptive performance. This gives us exclusive answer that how one can distinguish between personality and functioning. Researcher in this paper had focused on two courses of personality beliefs, beliefs about the softness of self-attitudes and prospect of societal reception versus refusal and describes the self-effacing interference has carried out about significant genuine humanity changes. Researcher concludes by signifying that personality beliefs are core values that individual

practice. That belief would co operate a more essential role in the personality. (Dweck, 2008)

In this Research paper consumer personality characters and consumer's attitudes is put in study to know its role. Author gives the idea that consumer attribute and personality has a major role in any industry as it can direct impact on the purchase behavior of the consumer. To know the personality of consumer and his behavior would help marketers to better survive in market and potent their position in the market. Researcher in this paper has focused on the personality troubles in consumer buying decision making mainly among the customer goods purchaser in the Khulna metropolitan area. The issue making personality problem in consumer buying decision in Khulna metropolitan area have been assessed by the given factors in the shape of: acquiescent, violent, separate for the neo-Freudian theory and obstinacy, require for exclusivity, communal spirit, consumer change, ethnocentrism and compulsiveness for trait theory. Researcher also discloses the troubles and recognized possible answers to overcome these troubles. (Sarker, et al., 2013)

This research examines consumer personality and its effect and connection among Stress connected assessment, consumption emotions, and the coping process towards consumer nature. Researcher in this paper has moderately experienced competitor model of these relationships. Research paper shows that consumer's perception of coping strategies are being influenced by the cognitive measures and personality characteristics. Researcher in this paper also gives the information about consumer behavior and tells us that it can be treated well with focusing on the personality & personality traits and personality models that surely manipulate the consumer. (Duhachek, et al., 2005)

The researcher in this paper has focused online shops to know the consumer spending in e business and their personality factors towards the online shopping instead of going to physical outlets. The reason of this editorial is mostly to examine the contact of personality traits of e-shoppers on their buying actions. Researcher in this paper has used the equation models and motivation models to know and analyze the personality of consumer and their behavior in online shopping. In last researcher has examined the buying decisions of consumers and relates it to their personality and personality traits, Researcher has also focused on the relation of personality, consumers and motivation level of consumers in this regard. (Tsao, et al., 2010)

Here in this research paper researcher aims to investigate the various arguments regarding the concept of personality and its correlation to consumer purchase behavior. Researcher has identified different problems that marketers face in analyzing consumer personality and consumer behavior. Researcher suggests that to defeat these blockades it will need exacting concentration to the plan or procedure of theory formulation. Both inductive and deductive approaches will be required in this regard. (Crosby, et al., 1984)

This research paper is based on the effect of brand personality and its relation with the personality, personality traits and consumer personality. Researcher wants to know the impact of brand personality and how it is being affected by the consumer buying behavior. Furthermore it involves the text on effects of brand personality in the some of these essential factors; examination about brand individuality might have diverse position along with representative vs. useful goods and taxing product qualities as a reasonable factor. (Oklevik, 2000)

Here in research paper author has given the idea about certain personality traits and said that it varies from one person to another, author has viewed different personality traits that control other personality traits and these are very inter related to each other. Researcher has also focused on the behavior of person that how it responds and co related with the personality. As consumer personality is also one of the essential aspects of consumer behavior. (Parvin, 1996).

This research paper is based on consumer behavior and his/her personality. In this paper authors are taking view of previous ages to know and judge the impact of previous era. Researcher said that consumer behavior varies from time to time as it was changed in 1970s, gradually changed in 1980s and again also 1990s it was observed that consumer respond in survey is totally different from others. Further thereby release two decades of research which has steadily moved toward revitalizing this area. Author also speaks about the rebirth of marketing in 1988s and has focused on the consumer personality. As researchers has also gone through the individual perspective of personality to go in depth study of personality. To judge the consumer response and also the group of author are willing to know some more implication regarding personality in general and specific.(Holbrook, 1990)

Author said that personality is the outcome of social and environmental influences on people mind. Author said that personality of person is sum of all his/her characteristics which he/she obtained from childhood. Author has given the general idea that each and every person is different from one and other in physical aspects and as well in personality. However that is personality of people that people respond in buying process and purchase decision is taken with the help of personality. Researcher also said that persons respond to the situations according to its surroundings. He said that these are the general response of people but we do not judge it. (Kasssarjian., 1981)

Here in this author has given the idea of personality while taking general view that people are not so much serious in taking any product according to their personality. Furthermore he has shared his experience of different conferences that what he has observed the view of speakers regarding personality of consumers. While working on personality of consumer he has given this idea that this is time to go back and look at the past seminar thinkers view about the personality that what was their thinking towards it and also judge present time as well and in last compare the difference. Author also thinks that personality different theories should be learnt using goods. There are also other things like buying and consumption of different products, so people are very much conscious about these exchange processes. Consumer personality plays essential role in it and also personality impact the motivation level of people. While author said that this is really a direct impact towards goal of gaining right product. Researcher views that if we will judge the consumer and his personality so we can take greater market place in the firm. Consumers are the really like backbone of man for any firm, as consumer personality has great potential to change the market scenario. Researcher also said that knowledge of consumer behavior can help us in making more power full strategies. (Gilson, 1986)

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study purposes to attain the following research objectives:

- To examine style adoption
- To identify the personality traits that influence style adoption

to get a clear sense of personality and its influence. He also said that personality has a dynamic impact on consumer thoughts that also influence consumer behavior. (Dylan, 1985)

This research paper focused on the personality and its traits. Researcher said that personality shows the uniqueness of the person. Personality is a key way to judge the attitude, behavior and individual preferences towards anything. Researcher also said that personality of consumer differs person to person and this is the basic reason that people are changed and different to each other. Their response is change and as well this changes the whole personality traits and this would be said endless as we cannot give accurate view about personality. However because of this we cannot segment the consumer. Personality is the factor that can change the market place of the product. Researcher said that if the firm knows the personality of person so it can get better market place for its product. (Hillix, 2006)

This research paper has focused on Consumer behavior and personality; the author said that it is the processes where there are certain things that vary according to consumer choices. It is judgment processes and acts of persons are involved in buying.

- To relate post-modern style adoption with personality traits
- To acquire better understanding of the role of gender and style adoption

4. RESEARCH PROBLEM

This study proposes a style-adoption model that investigates the elements prompting style adoption, and contributes to the academic field of consumer behavior. This study aims to explore post-modern style adoption among youth in Khairpur Mir's. For that reason, the key question guiding this study is:

“What personality factors effect style adoption among the youth in Khairpur Mir's”?

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

- The individual personality traits influence knowledge and attitude towards and decision to

adopt style.

- An individual's knowledge of style influences both their attitude towards, and decision to adopt, style

6. RESEARCH MODEL

7. METHODOLOGY

For the purposes of this study, comprehensive literature review is presented, in order to detect the factors that could influence style adoption. This information helped in the conceptual model development that is followed by the primary research. The research was a quantitative study in a sample of youth in and around Khairpur Mir's. A comparative study was undertaken, in an attempt to gather respondents' perceptions towards

modern style. The study findings will be presented against the proposed hypotheses, with analysis of the data done by using SPSS software.

7.1 Research Sampling

The people of interest are the youth in Khairpur Mir's. Probability sampling will encompass random selection of 85 full-time students from the University of the Shah Abdul Latif University, who will be asked to complete the questionnaires. The approximate age group of the respondents is 19 to 28 years, and the sample will consist of mixed gender and race categories.

7.3 Research Method

The research article methodology includes study propose. We have collected data via primary & secondary sources. A questionnaire survey was used by us to gather the information from the respondents and know the personality traits influencing style adoption among the youth in Khairpur Mir’s. To examine style adoption, to identify the personality traits that influence style adoption among youth, to compare post modern versus classic style adoption and to get a better understanding of the role of gender and style adoption. Ranking of the questionnaire was found on certain measures ranging from strongly agree to disagree consisting of scores from 1 to 5.

There one represents strongly agree and 5 denotes strongly disagree. As 54 items questionnaire was

prepared which was taken in its concluding form after the approval of the supervisor. To determine its reliability, data was entered in SPSS 16 for checking **Cronbach’s alpha** that equals to **0.877** than we explored the factors by using data reduction technique and finally linear regression with stepwise method was applied to check the influence of personality traits influencing style adoption among youth of Khairpur Mir’s.

The study of this research article is based on the personality traits that influence style adoption among youth of Khairpur Mir’s. The research location is considered relevant because of the appropriate result given by people. All people whom we surveyed in Khairpur Mir’s took active part for the completion of questionnaire surveys and returned to us.

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

8.1 Regression Stepwise Model Table 1

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.653	.427	.420	.765
2	.711	.506	.494	.715
3	.738	.545	.528	.690

As given table is of regression stepwise model which we explored by using SPSS 16 software via data reduction method that is linear regression stepwise method so it was observed that through this method the value of R Square gives the better results which are shown in the above table and shows the strong relation of style adoption with personality traits by giving the positive results where as SPSS 16 has excluded those factors which have negative impact and have weak relation for style adoption with personality traits.

In this the third model shown in table gives the better results compared to first and second and R square where shows that independent variables in the equation are rightly predicting the dependent variables and showing positive results and strong relation. R square also shows that the data we have collected to identify the influence of personality traits on style adoption is .545 is reliable

where is remaining are other variables of personality, but this is also a positive sign and shows the strong relation of personality traits which we have observed.

Here we have formed the equation for alpha and beta to show the relation in between dependant and independent variables, it will be easy for readers to get the accurate sense and understanding of the given table of regression stepwise model. Equation is:

$$(As = \alpha + KB1 + AB2 + FCB3 + SB4 + NUB5 + ICB6 + MFB7 + \text{Error term})$$

In this above equation R Square states the overall model fit means that higher the value of R square shows the strong and positive relation and lower the R square value shows the negative impact and weak relation of variables. Beta shows the degree of association of

independent and dependant variables.

8.2 Regression Coefficient Table 2

Model	Attitude	Susceptibility to interpersonal influence	Individualism/Collectivism
Standardized coefficient (Beta)	.449	.289	-.207
Std. Error	.089	.089	.079

Above given table shows the standardized beta coefficient results which are .449 for attitude having strong relation with style adoption, .289 for the susceptibility to interpersonal influence which also have positive impact towards the style adoption and in last individualism/collectivism has -.207 negative value but in comparison to other variables it has better value and have better relation with style adoption.

Furthermore SPSS 16 has included these three independent variables as a effective variables having positive and strong relationship with the dependent variable that is style adoption, while SPSS 16 has excluded all other variables because of their beta coefficient value was negative and there was weak relation of independent variables with dependent variable and it was also effecting the results of R square which was a not a positive sign.

9. CONCLUSION

It is predicted from the research that personality traits can affect and influence the style adoption among youth. Personality varies from person to person and it can be said that there are many traits are there for personality. The seven independent variables which we researched have impact on style adoption in youth of Khairpur Mir's. Attitude, susceptibility to interpersonal influence and individualism / collectivism of the people of Khairpur Mir's shows really a strong and effective

impact on style adoption among.

Furthermore some of factors were not showing the positive results yet these are good enough in relevance to style adoption. However as value of R square is .545, it means there are still many variables of personality that should be studied.

10. LIMITATIONS & FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This research study is property of our group and should not be copied as it is. It should be used as a guideline paper for other researchers. It is conducted to investigate the personality traits influencing style adoption among the youth in Khairpur Mir's. To know the personality traits influence on style adoption where as style adoption was dependent variable and personality traits were independent variables. So the views and thoughts are concerned with the youth of Khairpur Mir's and may not have any concern with other area.

Personality traits are many and it varies from person to person, here in this paper we have focused on eight traits of personality, among those one is dependent and other are independent variables, but there are also many other personality traits which should be given importance and studied by other scholars to promote the study of personality for future generation.

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